

MSPACE

Recommendations

Orkney Islands

Regional Marine Plan

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MSPACE
Marine Spatial Planning
Addressing Climate Effects

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1

What is MSPACE?

The Marine Spatial Planning Addressing Climate Effects programme (MSPACE) is a highly integrated, multidisciplinary and co-created research initiative, driving forward capability in designing and implementing economically viable and socially acceptable climate-smart marine plans (MSP) (i.e. marine plans that promote climate change adaptation and mitigation). MSPACE was designed to support the ambitions of government policy, the industrial sector, and communities to ensure sustainable management of marine resources and improve the marine environment for the next generation.

We co-created and explored with end-users alternative spatial management scenarios through which changes in marine space uses could enable climate change adaptation (and mitigation) for nature and people. Scenarios focused on actioning opportunities for climate-resilient conservation, fisheries and aquaculture, within the broader lens of marine planning and the many objectives for use of marine space held within the four MSPACE case study planning regions, as well as the wider push to deliver net zero in the UK.

2

Projected climate change impacts for Orkney

Supported by the UK Marine Climate Change Impacts Partnership (MCCIP, 2023), MSPACE first delivered a UK-level synthesis of projected impacts and opportunities that climate change will bring to our marine and coastal waters (Queirós et al., 2024). We assessed state-of-the-art climate change modelling projections for marine species and habitats, to help identify possible climate change adaptation (and mitigation) pathways for UK waters. We considered these results alongside the current distribution of seabed effects by sectors such as fisheries and dredging based on analyses undertaken in the UK for OSPAR and ICES (Sciberras et al., 2023). We also carried out a technical evaluation of our confidence in all modelling datasets used (Kay et al., 2023). We were then able to make recommendations for marine planning and other planning mechanisms in the UK, towards climate-resilient management of fisheries, aquaculture and marine conservation. Those results are detailed [here](#), and spatial datasets reflecting key findings can be found [here](#).

We estimated widespread climate change effects around the Orkney Islands, potentially impacting local conservation, fisheries and aquaculture activity. These findings were consistent when a range of emissions scenarios (2.4°C and 4°C mean global warming) were considered together. This range of futures represents the trajectory under current country commitments to the Paris Agreement and a worse trajectory, both exceeding the agreement’s aim to limit global warming below 2°C. Those findings suggested that **there is a limited scope for no-regrets spatial management opportunities in Orkney (that is, decisions that are effective and promote a sustainable marine environment despite climate change)** under this range of climate scenarios. Under the more moderate emissions trajectory, we found (Figure 1, top row):

- The design of the current network of conservation sites may need addressing to ensure it continues to contribute to an effective UK MPA network as our seas change into the future. This is due to the extensive distribution of climate change hotspots found to emerge throughout the Orkney Islands marine region (Figure 1, top row, left and middle) for benthic and pelagic habitats, and for benthic and pelagic megafauna.
- Important losses to the fishing and aquaculture sectors may occur, with climate change hotspots emerging also for both sectors (although we were not able to include key target species for Orkney Islands fishers our analysis - Velvet crab (*Necora puber*); European lobster (*Homarus Gammarus*) and king scallop (*Pecten maximus*) — [see here](#); Figure 1, top row, left and middle). Exploration of pelagic and other, potentially new species in the area may help address these losses, in the future.
- Climate change refugia for habitat conditions promoting carbon sequestration (i.e. “climate services”) emerged across most of the planning area. However, much of the sediment in Orkney is fairly coarse and more detailed analysis of local habitats would be required to identify suitable carbon conservation measures.

3

Exploration of alternative spatial management futures for Orkney Islands marine and coastal waters in support of climate change adaptation and mitigation

Due to the extent of climate change hotspots identified in results using modelling projections that considered a mean global warming of 4°C (RCP8.5), we focused the development of adaptation strategies for the waters surrounding Orkney Islands by focusing on a mean global warming future of 2.4°C only (RCP4.5, in line with current commitments to the Paris Agreement). To this end, MSPACE co-created and explored 4 alternative spatial management scenarios with Orkney Islands Marine Planning end-users, specifically, with the Orkney Islands Council, who have statutory responsibility for marine planning in OI. We started with:

Business as Usual: this scenario represents the current distribution of marine activities and conservation in the planning area, for which climate impacts were estimated (Queirós et al., 2024). This scenario is contrasted here with the **Baseline**, for which estimates are also provided, and which also reflect the current distribution of marine activities and conservation in the planning area, but excluded projected climate change effects in the region.

Three climate-smart scenarios were also co-created and explored: these scenarios targeted the development of regional opportunities for climate change adaptation or resilience for particular sectors, as well as climate change mitigation, based on changes in use of marine space (i.e. interventions) in climate change refugia (areas where particular sectors are estimated to have low sensitivity to climate change, Section 2). These three scenarios prioritised outcomes for different sectors:

Conservation: changes in spatial uses maximise climate change adaptation and mitigation outcomes through marine conservation.

Food Provision: changes in spatial uses maximise climate change adaptation for fisheries and aquaculture.

Compromise: considers outcomes for marine conservation, fisheries and aquaculture together, balancing overall climate change adaptation and mitigation goals in the region. This scenario was informed by prior assessment of the priorities of regional stakeholders with regard to marine space (Talbot et al., 2025).

Figure 1: Business as Usual (BAU) scenario (top row) in the Orkney Islands Regional Marine Plan Area, showing the location of benthic (left) and pelagic (middle) climate change hotspots as well as all refugia (right), for different groups of species, ecological function or sectors, under RCP4.5. Climate-smart scenarios co-developed are shown in the bottom row of figures, highlighting identified priority areas for different sectors in different scenarios (titles). A summary of co-created interventions to support adaptation (and mitigation) is given in the table.

Large sized figures of Priority Areas explored in each scenario are reprinted, with permission, from Talbot et al. in Annex 1.

C1: Avoid, minimise or mitigate activities which would be incompatible with the conservation of priority areas for benthic megafauna identified in Sanday SAC, Sule Skerry and Sule Stack SPA, and in waters to the east of the islands.

C2: Avoid, minimise or mitigate activities which could be incompatible with the conservation of a priority area for benthic habitats identified in waters to the west of Orkney.

C3: Avoid, minimise or mitigate activities which could adversely affect the climate services associated with protected features in the priority area for climate services identified in the North-West Orkney MPA.

FP1: Avoid, minimise or mitigate proposals for development and activities that are incompatible with access to priority areas for demersal and pelagic fisheries.

FP2: Avoid, minimise or mitigate proposals for activities that could limit the development of water column aquaculture in the identified priority areas for this sector.

CM1: Avoid, minimise or mitigate activities which would be incompatible with the conservation of priority areas for benthic megafauna identified in Sanday SAC, Sule Skerry and Sule Stack SPA, and in waters to the east of the islands.

CM2: Avoid, minimise or mitigate activities which could be incompatible with the conservation of a priority area for benthic habitats identified in waters to the west of Orkney.

CM3: Avoid, minimise or mitigate activities which could adversely affect the climate services associated with protected features in the priority area for climate services identified in the North-West Orkney MPA.

CM4: Avoid, minimise or mitigate proposals for uses that are incompatible with access to priority areas for demersal and pelagic fisheries.

CM5: Avoid, minimise or mitigate proposals for activities that could limit the development of water column aquaculture in the identified priority areas for this sector.

A summary of co-developed scenarios and their spatial interventions is given in Figure 1 and is described in detailed narrative in Talbot et al. (2025). Areas where changes to spatial management could lead to climate change adaptation for particular sectors (or mitigation) are hereafter referred to as **Priority Areas**, and specific proposed changes in spatial management in those areas referred to as **Interventions** (Figure 1).

The **performance of the BAU and of each climate-smart scenario was then estimated using environmental, economic and social criteria**, which were used to compare scenarios using this common set of metrics. These estimates can be seen in Table 1, where criteria estimates reflect projected change in each criterion relative to the Baseline scenario, given the projected regional impacts of climate change (BAU), and any additional changes in spatial management designed to promote climate change adaptation and mitigation. A detailed narrative and methodological description for these analyses can be found in Roca Florido et al. (2025) and Talbot et al. (2025).

We found that although climate change hotspots were widespread for most sectors, even under the moderate emissions scenario RCP4.5, climate change refugia (areas resilient to climate change) did provide opportunities to conserve climate services, benthic megafauna, benthic habitats, and for future, resilient pelagic fisheries and aquaculture activities using the water column (i.e. not the seabed; Figure 1, top row) though changes in the management of marine space. In MSPACE, we assessed the climate-resilience of aquaculture activities using the water column by analysis of ocean climate modelling data for key species cultured in the UK (salmon (*Salmo salar*), mussels (*Mytilus edulis*), sugar kelp (*Saccharina latissima*), as well for key environmental conditions used by these and other species farmed in the water column (such as halibut). Details of modelling data can be found [here](#) (Table S5).

According to those results, the **Conservation Scenario** (Figure 1) aimed to exploit identified refugia for climate services, benthic megafauna and benthic habitats. Refugia for benthic megafauna and benthic habitats conservation were identified and highlighted as priority areas supporting adaptation (**Interventions C1, C2** Figure 1), although these priority areas predominantly currently sit outside the existing MPA network. It is likely that **Intervention C1** (Figure 1) could support the recovery and climate-resilience of sharks, skates and rays of conservation and commercial interest in the Orkney region, while **Intervention C2** could maximise the effectiveness of the identified priority area in promoting the climate change resilience of benthic habitats. A refuge for climate services in the North-West Orkney MPA was identified as a potential priority area for climate regulation, and **Intervention C3** (Figure 1) could be used to help limit direct carbon release and degradation of important carbon stocks (avoided emissions) from sediment disturbing activities such as trawling. When compared to the BAU, small additional economic losses could be attributed to the three interventions in the Conservation scenario relative to the BAU, but these were much lower than the impacts estimated losses for the region driven by climate change (Baseline cf. BAU, Talbot et al. (2025), Table 1).

Through the **Food Provision Scenario** (Figure 1), we explored and identified priority areas for demersal fisheries, a priority area for water column aquaculture (co-located with the proposed West of Orkney windfarm), and an extensive priority area for pelagic fisheries, based on identified refugia (Figure 1). **Interventions FP1 & 2** (Figure 1) were therefore designed to help support these sectors in Orkney into the future, with substantial increases in jobs, wages and GVA estimated, relative to the BAU (Talbot et al. (2025), Table 1).

In the **Compromise Scenario**, we explored a combination of interventions from the other two climate-smart scenarios to deliver a balance of outcomes across sectors and climate goals. Through **Interventions CM1-5** (Figure 1) we identified benefits to the three MSPACE focal sectors, including increases in jobs, wages and GVA relative to the BAU (Talbot et al. (2025), Table 1).

4

Social acceptability of alternative hypothetical management scenarios

We tested the social acceptability of climate-smart scenario interventions (Figure 1) through online surveys of marine planning stakeholders, as detailed in Reinhardt (2026). A link to take the survey, which covered the 4 MSPACE case-studies, not just Orkney Islands, was shared widely via stakeholder networks and institutional social media networks. Each respondent was required to enter their name and organisation name to ensure no one took the survey more than once. Once collected and validated, survey responses were anonymised. During the survey, **respondents were able to access detailed information about the project and of co-created scenarios and their outcomes** (Marcone et al., 2026; Talbot et al., 2025). Of 112 unique and validated respondents, 30 answered the questions that relied on reading the information given, and 3 of these identified as being professionally active within the Orkney Islands Regional Marine Plan area, and an additional 2 respondents answered in a personal capacity. Their responses are summarised here, having been analysed using parametric and non-parametric methods in Reinhardt (2026).

This small number of Orkney specific responses does not enable us to draw statistically significant estimates of differences or trends across these respondents. However, examining the average responses and response differences across the 4 scenarios, and between responses provided with and without access to socio-economic outcomes (**Table 1**, p.13, as well as further evidence in Reinhardt (2026) we observe that:

- On average, respondents accepted climate-smart scenarios as alternatives to the BAU (acceptance scores ranging from 6-7.8 out of 10).
- On average, respondents always found the **Conservation Scenario** the most acceptable alternative to the BAU, whether they could only access information on the ecological outcomes of explored scenarios or their economic and social effects as well (7.80 +/- 1.64 (6.50 +/- 2.89), mean +/- standard deviation, without (with) economic and social outcomes information).
- The acceptance of climate-smart scenarios relative to the BAU was strongest when only ecological outcomes were available to survey respondents, and decreased moderately when economic and social outcomes were made available alongside ecological outcomes.
- The **Food Provision** scenario was always rated as only marginally acceptable as an alternative to the BAU, the lowest acceptability level of the climate-smart scenarios explored (6.00 +/- 1.41 , with and without economic and social outcomes estimates provided).
- The **Compromise Scenario** varied from the second most acceptable to only marginally acceptable as a climate-smart alternative to the BAU, when economic and social outcomes estimates were made available, alongside ecological outcomes information (7.00 +/- 0 (6.00 +/- 1.14), mean +/- standard deviation, without (with) economic and social outcomes information).

These results indicate a clear preference of survey respondents for climate-smart outcomes that protect nature in Orkney Islands relative to the BAU. This result could be interpreted as being well aligned with the vision and guiding principles of the Orkney Islands Regional Marine Plan, which emphasises sustainable marine development, activities and use of marine space, in line with the need to protect (and enhance) the marine environment and ecosystems, on which local communities are seen to depend. The acceptance of climate-smart scenarios is also well aligned with the plan's vision to address climate change. However, economic and social considerations were key concerns for respondents, that reduced the acceptance of all explored climate-smart scenarios. Notably, the Food Provision Scenario and the Compromise Scenario were only marginally acceptable as alternatives if economic and social outcomes estimated were made available to respondents. These results suggest, therefore, that while the health of the marine environment under climate change is seen as an issue of importance, any measures to tackle climate change in the marine environment and activities in the waters surrounding Orkney Islands should be clearly designed to ensure economic and social outcomes are also maximised. This would also ensure close alignment with several policies within the Orkney Islands Regional Marine Plan (Objective 5; General Policy 1bi; General Policy 4).

5

Multiple criteria decision analysis

Multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA, Marcone et al., 2026) was used to help establish indirectly how the performance of co-created scenarios (Figure 1) aligns with the intrinsic preferences of key marine planning stakeholders (who had previously engaged with MSPACE) over the assessed list of criteria (Table 1).

The MSPACE team first estimated scenario performance on each criterion, which were combined into the Orkney Islands scenario performance matrix (Table 1; Marcone et al. 2026). Then, an online MCDA survey was used, mainly targeting experts already involved in MSPACE and marine planning in Orkney Islands, who were individually contacted by email. During an online interview, respondents were presented with background information about the project and the survey objectives, and answered questions designed to understand their preferences on the criteria list. Importantly, respondents answered questions **without knowing how co-created scenarios performed on assessment criteria (Figure 1, Table 1)**. The MSPACE team then estimated scenario performance on each criterion, which were combined into the scenario performance matrix (Table 1; Marcone et al. 2026). The performance matrix was then analysed together with preference information collected from respondents through the MCDA survey to rank scenarios accordingly (Table 1). Details of the analyses leading to the scenario rankings listed in Table 1 can be found in Marcone et al. (2026).

Overall, the intrinsic preferences of Orkney Islands marine region respondents were found to be better aligned with the **Compromise Scenario** (rank=1), and were consistently less aligned with Conservation scenario (rank = 4), with the compromise and BAU scenarios with intermediate ranks (Table 1). Based on these results, it is suggested that marine **planning stakeholders in Orkney Islands intrinsically support adaptation to climate change, and prefer interventions that deliver adaptation across sectors**. These results are in line with the interpretation of the results from section 4, which highlighted both a concern with nature and social and economic impacts of ocean management, with support for climate-smart alternatives to the BAU. However, **the MCDA results indicate that stakeholders' intrinsic preferences can be challenged with evidence is provided on specific management decisions under consideration**, as explored in MSPACE through co-developed scenarios. This was made evident by the greater acceptance of the Conservation Scenario (Section 4) despite the Compromise scenario also being available.

Assessment criteria					Baseline*	Scenario performance matrix (% change on Baseline) **					
	Short name (used in survey)	Unit	Scenario design	BAU		Conservation	Food provision	Compromise			
ENVIRONMENTAL	1	a.1	Climate-resilient MPA	km2	maximise	2494.19	485	510.6	485	510.6	
	2	a.2	Climate-resilient fishery area	km2	maximise	7531.87	667.7	502.4	667.7	578.4	
	3	a.3	Climate-resilient aquaculture area	km2	maximise	5.18	-100	-100	7187.3	5842.3	
	4	a.4	Total greenhouse gas emissions	kt CO2e/yr	minimise	1.88	1374	1317.4	7824.1	6255.2	
	5	a.5	Potential for marine renewable energy	MW	maximise	32652.7	0	0	0	0	
SOCIAL	6	b.1	Jobs in the food production sector	nr of jobs	maximise	377	-77.5	-78.1	35.6	9	
	7	b.2	Job in the recreation and tourism sector	nr of jobs	maximise	0.06	1669.6	1645.5	11303.6	9150.3	
ECONOMIC	8	c.1	Economic contribution of the food production sector (GVA)	£ (millions)	maximise	3.4	870.2	851.5	6043	4879.8	
	9	c.2	Income in the food production sector (wages)	£ (millions)	maximise	2.1	743.7	727.5	5242.2	4230.7	
	10	c.3	Economic contribution of the recreation and tourism sector (GVA)	£ (millions)	maximise	0.001	2324.1	2291.2	15522.1	12572.2	
	11	c.4	Income in the recreation and tourism sector (wages)	£ (millions)	maximise	0	0	0	0	0	
Scenario ranking based on stakeholder acceptance of climate-smart scenario relative to BAU (without/with social-economic evidence, Section 4)								1/1	3/joint 2	2/joint 2	
Aggregated Scenario ranking based on implicit stakeholder preferences (Section 5)								3	4	2	1

*Baseline values give the current distribution of marine activities and ignore the impacts of future climate change.

** Percent change on Baseline is calculated as: % = 100-(100*(Scenario criterion estimate /Baseline criterion estimate))

Table 1. Criteria used to assess the performance of co-created alternative spatial management scenarios, and the mean acceptability (Section 4) and implicit preference of stakeholders of said scenarios (Section 5). "GVA" stands for Gross Value Added of a given sector. Changes across scenarios are given as % changes on the baseline numbers.

6

Recommendations

6.1. Stakeholders of the Orkney Islands Regional Marine Plan want climate adaptation for nature

We recommend, based on our direct stakeholder survey and knowledge co-creation activities, that the spatial management interventions developed during the MSPACE scenario co-creation could help address climate change in Orkney Islands. Of particular relevance are interventions developed under the **Conservation Scenario** to increase the climate resilience of nature as well as the protection of seabed carbon storage (Figure 1, above):

Intervention C1: could support the recovery and climate-resilience of sharks, skates and rays of conservation interest in the Orkney region, some of which are also exploited by fisheries.

Intervention C2: could maximise the effectiveness of the identified conservation priority area in promoting the climate change resilience of benthic habitats, with benefits for nature and local fisheries.

Intervention C3: could be used to help limit direct carbon release and degradation of important carbon stocks from sediment disturbing activities such as trawling.

Areas identified in these interventions that are adjacent to the foreshore (e.g. blue carbon habitats) and their protection could be strengthened through the management of activities under the umbrella of the Regional Marine Plan, under the responsibility of the Orkney Islands Council. However, several sites are outside of the current network of designated sites around the Orkney Islands, such that changes to their management would require additional legislation and support from national government.

However, MSPACE research also suggests that any activities that should affect the spatial management of the marine waters surrounding Orkney Islands also require in depth consideration of how they affect marine activity sectors. Over both stakeholder surveys, the **Compromise** seemed a better reflection of stakeholder implicit preferences, although the Conservation scenario was chosen during acceptability surveys. These results therefore suggest that there is scope for a climate-smart approach to spatial management in the waters around Orkney Islands, but more work is probably still required to further refine future interventions.

6.2. Translating climate change evidence into metrics stakeholders can relate to is key to assess buy-in for adaptation and mitigation through management of marine space

We recommend presenting Orkney planning stakeholders with specific, alternative spatial management options (including the status-quo, i.e. Business as Usual) during consultations on marine planning (Figure 1). We also recommend presenting estimates of the environmental, economic and social effects estimated for the spatial management alternatives consulted upon, as shown here in Table 1. This allows stakeholders to give informed, evidence-based views about specific changes to spatial management that may be under consideration (Section 4), rather than expressing general views about which topics matter the most to them (Section 5). MSPACE found that by exploring concrete options for spatial management and estimates of ecological, economic and social effects can help challenge pre-conceived notions individuals may hold about the cost or impact of addressing climate change to them or their sector (Section 4 cf. Section 5). This also presents a fairer and more transparent way to help decision-makers assess which decisions may best represent the interests of stakeholders, and thus what changes to spatial management that could help address climate change may be best suited to their region.

a. Wider marine planning for climate change adaptation and mitigation in Orkney Islands

We co-created alternative spatial management interventions with planning stakeholders to support climate change adaptation and mitigation in the Orkney Islands (Figure 1), and we measured that these interventions are seen by planning stakeholders in Orkney as preferable to the status-quo (Reinhardt 2026, Marcone et al. 2026). Such interventions are not directly regulated by Marine Plans in Scotland, and their actioning is further complicated in the Orkney Islands by cutting across national and regional policy. However, as we look to the future, the current review of the UK Marine Policy Statement, the upcoming Scottish National Marine Plan 2, and the current momentum for more spatial prescription in Marine Plans across the UK may allow for more explicit considerations of these strategies, especially now the Orkney Islands Regional Marine Plan has been approved (2026) and we enter implementation. That momentum is likely to be an important enabler for the Climate Change (Scotland) Act (2009) and Scotland's Climate Change Adaptation Programme 2019 to 2024 (Scottish Government, 2023). Furthermore, analysis of the consultation on the National Marine Plan 2 Planning Position Statement suggest stakeholders are overwhelmingly in favour of giving significant weight to the climate and nature crises in Scottish Planning (Scottish Government, 2025). This joined up willingness to act on nature and climate was also recognised within the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change's Glasgow Climate Pact 2021, which emerged from the Convention of Parties 21 hosted in the UK, and to which the UK is a signatory party. The Pact highlighted how biodiversity can help provide both climate change adaptation and mitigation benefits. Interventions which seek to improve the adaptation and mitigation potential of the marine environment, as discussed in this document, while protecting critical biodiversity (Interventions C1-3), may therefore also contribute to Scotland's legally binding target of achieving net zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050.

The landscape of planning mechanisms is developing across the UK (e.g. Fisheries Management Plans (Joint Fisheries Statement, 2022)), and new opportunities are emerging for the designation of conservation sites as a consequence of compensatory measures to support the delivery of net-zero (Department for Energy Security & Net Zero, 2025; Ward, 2022). In this context, **we recommend** that these different planning mechanisms must be well integrated with each other and with the implementation of planning policy mechanisms such as the Orkney Islands Regional Marine Plan. This integration will be key to ensure that mutual objectives on adaptation and mitigation, across policies and across the UK nations are supported well. Indeed, recent research by this team highlighted that siloed approaches to policy and governance, across sectors and across nations, are key stumbling blocks limiting opportunities to deliver climate action through the management of marine space (Queirós et al., 2025). The MSPACE project invested in the co-creation of potential solutions to help address climate change in Orkney Islands and the UK as a whole. These solutions have the best chance of becoming actionable through an enabling and well-integrated marine planning policy and governance landscape across the UK nations.

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Annex 1

Individual co-developed scenario figures, reproduced, with permission, from Talbot et al. 2025.

Figure S1 Conservation Scenario: locations of the priority areas for conservation of benthic habitats, benthic megafauna and climate services. In Talbot et al. 2025

Figure S2 Food Provision Scenario:

locations of priority areas for demersal fisheries, pelagic fisheries and water column aquaculture. In Talbot et al. 2025.

Figure S3 Compromise Scenario: locations of revised priority areas for conservation, demersal fisheries, pelagic fisheries and water column aquaculture. In Talbot et al. 2025

Marine Spatial Planning Addressing Climate Effects (MSPACE) was a highly integrated, multidisciplinary research project, designed to drive forward the capability of the four UK nations in designing and implementing economically viable and socially acceptable climate-smart marine plans. The project was co created with UK governments, the policy community, marine industries and communities to ensure sustainable management of UK marine resources and improve the marine environment for the next generation.

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The MSPACE initiative continues as an endorsed UN Ocean Decade Action, helping deliver the vision of the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development 2021-2030.

MSPACE
Marine Spatial Planning
Addressing Climate Effects